

Multiple Instance Learning for Detecting Crowd Behavior Anomalies in Surveillance Videos

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Abstract— This paper considers the stimulating task of video anomaly detection, which has received growing attention in the last decade with numerous applications in the real world, the most recognized one being the crowd behavior anomaly detection system. To achieve this task, the paper makes use of a dataset consisting of around 1400 videos, including both normal and anomalous videos, with 7 classes of anomalies in all. We extracted both spatial and temporal features from the videos and processed them to obtain 13D features. Further, we experimented with 9 different sets of classifiers and tabulated the results obtained in each case. On testing our model against the popular UCF-Crime dataset, we obtained an AUC of 0.846, which is on par with state-of-the-art systems, and an AUC of 0.886 on a subset of the dataset made up of the 7 classes representing crowd behavior anomalies. Furthermore, the model makes use of a weakly-supervised approach as opposed to supervised and unsupervised modes.

Keywords—Video Anomaly Detection, Anomaly, Weakly-Supervised, Spatial, Temporal.

I. INTRODUCTION

Video Anomaly Detection (VAD) has been a challenging task to tackle in the past decade. Based on the results of a survey conducted in 2021, the number of surveillance cameras across the globe is expected to surge to 1 billion in the near future and monitoring such a large number of cameras is practically impossible for humans. It would consume both time and money, hence the need of the hour is to develop systems capable of detecting anomalies and raising an alert to the concerned authorities. In this paper, we introduce a multiple-instance learning model to specifically address crowd behavior anomalies. These anomalies include, but are not restricted to: abuse, arrest, fighting, shoplifting, burglary, and robbery.

Surveillance cameras are installed at different locations with varying needs. While the cameras installed on the roadside are used to track violations of rules on the road, accidents, or possibly a fight between different individuals or groups due to an unknown reason. On the other hand, the purpose of installing surveillance cameras in shopping marts, malls, etc. is to track abnormal events like shoplifting, burglary, stealing, and robbery. In most other places, including schools, hospitals, elevators, etc., the main agenda is to track abnormal events like assault, fighting, abuse, etc. Hence, one commonality in all the above cases is that crowd behavior anomaly detection is one of the major use cases of surveillance cameras. Therefore, any automated system which aims to detect anomalies using CCTV videos as input must be capable of detecting these anomalies, and should be as accurate as possible in doing so. In this paper,

we have considered 7 classes of anomalies with 592 anomalous videos and 810 normal videos for training. For testing, we have used 140 anomalous videos and 150 normal videos.

There are 3 different ways in which VAD can be performed. The first approach is a supervised approach. In this approach, the videos would have to be labeled at a video-level as well as clip-level. This is very time-consuming since labeling all videos is a very tedious task, which requires skilled workers and training would, in turn, prove to be highly resource-intensive. The second approach is an unsupervised approach. In this situation, no labeled data is needed, and the model is required to learn all the video-features from the dataset by itself. Although this would be the ideal case, such models are very data-hungry and require a large amount of data to provide accurate classification results. This led us towards the optimized approach which does not require too much human effort, and does not require 100's of GBs of data to learn. It is a weakly-supervised approach in which videos are labeled at the video-level but not at the clip-level.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section II describes significant related work in the domain. Section III presents the methodology adopted in detail, while Experiments and Results are listed in Section IV. We close with conclusions and future scope for this work.

II. RELATED WORK

In this section, the previous research conducted in this domain has been stated in brief. In [1], the task of VAD has been tackled by adopting a weakly supervised approach. This approach exploits the concept of Multiple-Instance Learning, which splits the data into 2 bags: a positive bag and a negative bag. The positive bag consists of anomalous videos and the negative bag consists of normal videos. Since a weakly-supervised approach has been employed, the videos have been labeled at the video-level and not at the clip-level, which would be impractical to achieve manually. The videos have further been divided into segments consisting of 16 frames each, and these segments are referred to as instances in the bag. Each anomalous segment consists of at least 1 anomalous frame, while normal segments consist of all normal frames. A deep anomaly ranking model is trained which predicts high scores for anomalous videos and low scores for normal videos. This paper was the first to introduce a large-scale video dataset consisting of more than 1000 videos consisting of 13

different classes of real-world anomalies in addition to normal videos. The anomalies include but are not limited to abuse, arson, assault, arrest, accident, burglary, fighting and robbery. The UCF-Crime dataset introduced in this paper consists of carefully selected videos for each category and has been used for comparison of the performance of newly emerging approaches ever since. The approach adopted in this paper is similar to [1], with the differentiating factor being the class of anomalous videos the model is trained on. Instead of training a robust model using such a broad class of anomalies, which is highly data and resource intensive, in addition to being time-consuming, we have restricted the anomaly class to solely abnormal crowd behavior. This is one of the primary requirements in real-world situations and hence, we have addressed this problem.

[2] considers a different approach from [1] at the feature extraction stage. In place of extracting I3D features using a 3D convolutional network, as in [1], [2] adopts a temporal segment network (TSN) for this purpose. TSN, offers a distinctive method for capturing temporal information by dividing videos into segments and aggregating features across these segments. This alternative technique in [2] provides a nuanced perspective on temporal feature extraction compared to the 3D convolutional approach employed in [1]. However, our choice of MIL is driven by its inherent advantages. TSN, despite its effectiveness in capturing temporal information, may encounter limitations in scenarios where anomalies manifest as subtle deviations over extended time intervals. MIL, on the other hand, excels at discerning anomalous instances within video sequences, enabling a more granular identification of irregularities. This is particularly beneficial in applications where anomalies may be sporadic or occur in localized segments, showcasing the superiority of MIL in certain real-world anomaly detection scenarios.

[3] introduces a novel approach to video anomaly detection by combining the strengths of an autoencoder and a discriminator within a Generative Adversarial Network (GAN) framework. In contrast to conventional methods such as [1], which predominantly rely on feature extraction using 3D convolutional networks, this model leverages the power of adversarial training for enhanced anomaly detection.

Building upon the autoencoder architecture, [3] employs a 3D convolutional autoencoder for feature learning and reconstruction. This differs from the temporal segment network (TSN) utilized in [2] for feature extraction. Furthermore, the GAN architecture introduces a discriminator component, training the model in an adversarial manner. This adversarial training strategy, absent in conventional methods [1] and [2], enhances the model's ability to generate realistic frames while effectively distinguishing between real and generated frames.

Multiple Instance Learning (MIL) presents a superior choice over Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) for video anomaly detection due to its inherent strengths in discerning anomalous instances. While GANs primarily focus on generating realistic frames, MIL is tailored for identifying subtle irregularities within video sequences. MIL excels in scenarios where anomalies manifest as sporadic deviations over extended time intervals, offering a more granular and effective approach to anomaly detection. The nuanced perspective provided by MIL contributes to its superiority in capturing and isolating irregularities, making it well-suited for real-world applications compared to the broader focus of GANs on frame generation.

[4] introduces the use of two-stream Inflated 3D ConvNet to video anomaly detection, addressing challenges

in identifying abnormal events in surveillance videos. Leveraging a two-stream inflated 3D convolutional network and a weakly supervised anomaly detection framework named Anomaly Regression Net (AR-Net), the proposed model is evaluated on the UCF-Crime dataset, focusing on limited anomalies – namely abuse, arrest, assault, fight, arson, and explosion. Further, for the feature extraction stage, as in this paper, I3D is used as the feature extractor. Using the output from the feature extractor as the input to AR-Net, a custom loss function which reduces intra-class variance is included. For the reduced dataset with the classes mentioned above, the approach in [4] has the highest accuracy compared to other approaches.

[5] makes use of motion information images (MII) to distinguish normal and abnormal frames. It focuses on global abnormal crowd behaviour detection (social force model- interaction force of particles placed on an image plane). The process is divided into two steps- Event Representation (spatial-temporal features-optical flow histogram) and Anomaly Measurement (makes use of one class learning methods-HMM, SVM). The method is largely dependent on two features- optical flow magnitude and angle difference between optical flow vectors of consecutive frames, with the optical flow being calculated using the Lucas-Kanade algorithm. The optical flow magnitude of the current frame is multiplied by the angle difference in order to be resistant to noise and lighting changes. This way the MII is invariant to the direction of motion, making it a robust approach. These MIIs are then used to train the CNN. However, the formation of MIIs is a time-taking process.

[6] develops an interesting approach, it utilizes an Incremental Spatiotemporal Learner (ISTL) which is an active learner with fuzzy aggregation. The continual learning approach it adopts addresses the evolving nature of anomalies and normality. An auto-encoder with CNN is employed to learn the spatial features, and a Convolution LSTM (ConvLSTM) is used to learn the temporal features. A reconstruction error threshold is used to distinguish between normal and abnormal videos, and a temporal threshold is used to define the number of frames that need to be abnormal for the event to be classified as an anomaly, this reduces false positives. A human observer validates the detected anomalies, this validation input is used to update normal behaviour (normality of learner) using fuzzy aggregation. This human feedback is the key to capturing novel normal behaviour while still being stable to detecting previous normal behaviour.

[7] introduces a reinforcement learning based approach-Deep Q Learning Network (DQN) to localize anomalies in videos, which also enables the agent to learn how to detect and recognize the abnormalities in videos. It employs a selection process to pick the most representative anomaly segments from the video input, compacting the action space. The agent provides estimation feedback from the environment, and teaches the learner using its recognition performance which indicates the quality of the input segments. To make the reinforcement learning agent understand the dynamics of its surroundings on its own- other than the reward and the state, the environment doesn't give the agent any additional feedback. The design is largely based on a dueling structure, which relies on two different sub-networks. It also makes use of prioritized experience replay which changes the sampling distribution of transition tuples, to define the priority of each tuple of experience. This paper explores multiple techniques for reinforcement

learning, some of which show great progress in network noise-reduction.

[8] makes use of transfer learning to significantly reduce training complexity and extract pertinent features from the input video. It uses YOLOv3 to detect objects and monitors the center of the bounding box to obtain location features, while optical flow features are monitored using FlowNet 2. Using the appearance, motion, and location features extracted, a feature vector is constructed. It introduces N-shot video sequential anomaly detection, which learns continually even with scarce samples. kNN Euclidian distance is then used to differentiate between detected patterns and training data points where anomalous instances will have statistically higher kNN distances in comparison to nominal data points. The decision threshold is chosen using an asymptotic performance analysis by the sequential anomaly detector. This method performs noticeably better than other models in terms of any-shot learning of new nominal patterns.

[9] introduces a Dissimilarity Attention Module (DAM) that incorporates local contextual information rather than global context in the anomaly detection for real-time applications. The framework learns a discriminative representation for anomaly instances at both feature and score levels. It uses 3D ConvNet to extract spatio-temporal features and construct a feature map. A combination of LSTM and DAM is used to learn a discriminative representation for anomalies and normal instances. The two channels in the DAM highlight both the clip-level encoded feature vector and the temporal clips, which guide the ranking loss function for effective differentiation. A multi-layer perceptron takes the DAM modulated clips and assigns individual detection scores using a sigmoid activation function. Although this approach outperformed state-of-the-art models and is significantly faster, it demonstrated a high rate of false positives.

III. METHODOLOGY

This section describes the steps adopted during the extraction of spatio-temporal features, the nature of the dataset chosen and the implementation details.

A. Dataset

The UCF-Crime dataset is a large-scale dataset of 128 hours of videos. It consists of 1900 long and untrimmed real-world surveillance videos, with 13 realistic anomalies including Abuse, Arrest, Arson, Assault, Road Accident, Burglary, Explosion, Fighting, Robbery, Shooting, Stealing, Shoplifting, and Vandalism. These anomalies are selected because they have a significant impact on public safety.

This dataset can be used for two tasks. First, general anomaly detection considering all anomalies in one group and all normal activities in another group. Second, for recognizing each of 13 anomalous activities.

Video Class	Number of Videos	Training Videos	Testing Videos	Length (HH:MM:SS)
Abuse	50	48	2	01:45:54
Assault	50	47	3	00:56:07
Burglary	100	87	13	04:21:39
Fighting	50	45	5	02:23:52
Robbery	150	145	5	03:54:27
Shooting	50	29	21	03:00:14
Stealing	100	95	5	04:19:46
Normal Videos	940	810	150	75:40:27
Total	1490	1306	204	

Table 1. Breakdown of the used dataset.

In our paper, we have considered only 7 anomalous classes which relate to crowd behavior, namely: abuse, assault, burglary, fighting, robbery, shoplifting, and stealing.

B. Feature Extraction

Video features encompass distinctive elements extracted from video sequences that facilitate understanding and analysis. These features encapsulate spatial and temporal characteristics, such as color, texture, motion, and temporal patterns. Effective video feature extraction is crucial for tasks like video classification, anomaly detection, and action recognition. Spatial features capture static information within frames, while temporal features account for dynamic changes over time. Robust video features play a pivotal role in enabling accurate modeling and interpretation of video content, empowering applications across various domains, including surveillance, entertainment, and healthcare.

A brief overview of the features considered is as shown:

1) *C3D*: C3D comprises of 3x3x3 convolutional kernels followed by a 2x2x2 pooling at each layer. It exhibits a homogenous design unlike other pre-trained models (ResNets and AlexNet). Since it was trained on large supervised datasets like UCF-101 and Sports 1M, it specializes in extraction of both spatial and temporal components. Action localization and event detection are made possible by C3D's generic feature extraction, which eliminates the need for fine-tuning. Small 3 x 3 x 3 kernel sizes in the homogeneous architecture of the model ensure quick and effective inference, which makes it especially appropriate for embedded platforms that are essential in smart camera environments for real-time processing and metadata extraction in surveillance and smart city applications.

Figure 1. C3D Architecture [10].

2) *I3D*: Inflated 3D ConvNets, or I3Ds, is a feature-rich architecture that extends 2D CNNs to 3D space with ease and is specifically intended for video understanding. I3D preserves both spatial and temporal information by inflating its filters into 3D kernels, building on a pre-trained 2D model. For improved video representation, the network uses two-stream architectures that capture appearance and motion cues. I3D is a powerful tool for action recognition and detection tasks because it extracts spatiotemporal features well by using inflated 3D convolutions followed by pooling. Because it has been pre-trained on large-scale datasets such as Kinetics, it is versatile and can extract robust features without requiring a lot of task-specific fine-tuning.

Figure 2. I3D Architecture [11].

3) *TSN*: By separating videos into temporal segments and aggregating features across these segments, Temporal Segment Networks (TSN) offer a novel method for comprehending videos. Wang et al.'s method in [12] improves temporal modelling without sacrificing spatial information. In order to accomplish this, TSN samples a sparse collection of video frames, allowing for effective processing while preserving temporal context. The network consists of a strong blend of 2D CNNs and sparse temporal sampling, which enhances performance in action recognition tasks and allows for efficient feature extraction. Because TSN provides a unique approach to capturing temporal dynamics, it is an architecture that is useful in situations where temporal information is critical, like action recognition in multiple video sequences.

Figure 3. TSN Overview [12].

4) *ResNext*: An important concept called "cardinality" is introduced in ResNeXt, an evolution of the ResNet architecture, to improve model performance. ResNeXt allows the network to learn diverse representations more efficiently by enabling multiple parallel paths within each residual block through the use of a user-defined cardinality parameter. This increased parallelism leads to state-of-the-art performance on image classification benchmarks, as the model is better able to capture complex features. The architecture uses a bottleneck design to strike a compromise between computational efficiency and feature richness while preserving the essential ResNet building blocks, such as residual blocks with skip connections. ResNeXt is well-known for its scalability and versatility.

In this paper, we have used I3D features for the feature extraction stage.

C. Implementation Details

In our study, we leveraged PyTorch as the primary deep-learning framework for the implementation of our proposed model. The classifier architecture is composed of three fully connected layers, with rectified linear unit (ReLU) activation functions applied after the first two layers, followed by a Softmax activation in the final layer. This design ensures effective feature extraction and non-linearity in the decision-making process. Notably, the last output of the classifier provides an anomaly score, ranging between 0 and 1, facilitating a nuanced interpretation of the model's confidence in classifying instances. To optimize the network's discriminative capabilities, we employed a Multiple Instance Learning (MIL) framework with a ranking loss. This allowed our model to learn from both normal and anomalous instances, enhancing its ability to discern subtle irregularities within video sequences.

IV. EXPERIMENTATION AND RESULTS

A. Experiments

Our experimental evaluation involved a rigorous analysis of the proposed model's performance on various subsets of the dataset using key performance metrics, which include AUC, Precision, Recall and F1-Score and Loss. We tested the model with a range of classifiers that we engineered that differ architecturally in layers, streams, ratio of feature reductions and type of activation functions. The model underwent comprehensive training and evaluation phases, with hyperparameter tuning for learning rate, activation functions, optimizers, batch size, and dropout rate for optimal performance.

Figure 4. Learner-1 Architecture.

Figure 5. Learner-2 Architecture.

Figure 6. Learner-3 Architecture.

Figure 7. Learner-4 Architecture.

Figure 8. Learner-5 Architecture.

Figure 9. Learner-6 Architecture.

Figure 10. Learner-8 Architecture.

Figure 11. Learner-9 Architecture.

Learner-1 was sourced from *Sultani et al.* [1], which is a simple single-stream network with Sigmoid and ReLU activation functions. Learner-4, 5 and 6 are all single stream networks as well. 4 includes a residual block to skip layers, this addition of a residual network contributed to a higher AUC than seen in previous learners. 5 has ReLU paired with dropout intermediately. Additionally, attention weights have been included in an attempt to process spatial and temporal features one at a time. 6 comprises of 7 linear layers paired with ReLU. The AUC obtained with 6 was 0.828, which is high for a single-stream network.

Learner-2 is a newer iteration of [1], which improves the AUC of the model significantly by adding layer normalization and making it a 2-stream network. Learner-3 and 9 are similar to Learner-2. 2 utilizes LeakyReLU and Sigmoid in one stream, and ReLU and TanH in another. 9 has 4 linear layers with ReLU and Sigmoid as activation functions.

Learner-8 is a 3-stream network built motivated by the positive results obtained on moving from single-stream to 2-stream networks. Stream 1 consists of 3 linear layers coupled with ReLU and dropout. Stream 2 is similar to stream 1, with layer normalization in addition. Lastly, stream 3 consists of 3 linear layers coupled with LeakyReLU and no dropout. The output from these layers is combined with attention weights and the output anomaly score is obtained. As anticipated, learner 8 provided the best results in comparison with an AUC of 0.846.

B. Results

The results, summarized in the tables below, reveal that learner 8 emerged as the most promising classifier. The

selection of learner 8 was based on a trade-off analysis considering AUC, precision, and recall. This classifier demonstrated the ability to balance these metrics, showcasing superior anomaly detection performance compared to its counterparts.

The primary aim while building the network is to find the optimal trade-off between high precision, high recall, and high AUC. While high recall is undoubtedly the most important criterion, i.e., reducing the number of false negatives and ensuring that maximum number of anomalies are detected correctly, the precision should also be considerably high. This is because having a low precision would consequently result in more manual intervention to confirm if the threat raised was genuine or false. This defeats the entire purpose of an automated anomaly detection system. Hence, AUC is considered the most relevant parameter for evaluation of the system. A system with a high AUC and ideally high precision and recall is desired by the user.

The success of learner 8, coupled with hyperparameter optimization, underscores the effectiveness of the anomaly detection system. The precision-recall balance, along with a high AUC, positions the model as a robust solution. Notably, the utilization of the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 0.01 proved superior, leveraging its fast convergence and adaptive characteristics. This not only contributed to superior AUC but also minimized the trade-off between precision and recall. The results, as illustrated in the experimentation graph, emphasize the system's efficiency in automated threat detection.

Classifiers	AUC	Loss
Classifier-1	0.8288	0.4417
Classifier-2	0.83888	0.14
Classifier-3	0.83605	0.50
Classifier-4	0.84496	0.25
Classifier-5	0.8184	0.54
Classifier-6	0.8284	0.73
Classifier-7	0.8359	0.21
Classifier-8	0.846	0.25
Classifier-9	0.82	0.84

Table 2. Classifier performance on original UCF-Crime dataset.

Learner	AUC	Precision	Recall	F1
1	0.9013	0.596	0.5255	0.364
2	0.9012	0.546	0.5785	0.3904
3	0.8987	0.5789	0.5432	0.378
4	0.8976	0.6685	0.4168	0.3227
5	0.8963	0.6429	0.4315	0.3648
6	0.8965	0.777	0.2828	0.3212
7	0.8855	0.8155	0.2247	0.2242
8	0.8859	0.6158	0.5597	0.4174
9	0.8449	0.3335	0.8573	0.4009

Table 3. Classifier performance on 7-class crowd behaviour relevant dataset.

S.No.	Learning Rate	Optimiser	AUC	Precision	Recall	F1	Loss
1	0.001 (Default)	Adam (Default)	0.8922	0.6106	0.4879	0.4090	0.07682
2	0.0005	Adam	0.8976	0.6098	0.5096	0.4078	0.09341
3	0.005	Adam	0.8870	0.6375	0.4601	0.3912	0.10640
4	0.01	Adam	0.8754	0.7004	0.4307	0.3695	0.12338
5	0.1	Adam	0.8435	0.4986	0.4990	0.4084	0.2266
6	0.0001	Adam	0.8950	0.6215	0.4349	0.3981	0.1702
7	0.0005	Adadelta	0.6453	0.1351	0.9952	0.2141	0.9936
8	0.001 (Default)	Adadelta	0.7837	0.1289	0.9561	0.2077	0.9787
9	0.005	Adadelta	0.8210	0.5951	0.3233	0.4382	0.8619
10	0.05	Adadelta	0.8923	0.7814	0.2652	0.3012	0.2343
11	0.1	Adadelta	0.9011	0.6530	0.4603	0.3920	0.1455
12	0.2	Adadelta	0.9062	0.6777	0.4193	0.3631	0.1316
13	0.5	Adadelta	0.8955	0.5877	0.5328	0.3905	0.1020
14	0.9	Adadelta	0.8954	0.6012	0.5573	0.4431	0.1026
15	0.001	Adagrad	0.8968	0.7127	0.3484	0.2923	0.2507
16	0.01	Adagrad	0.8966	0.6391	0.4720	0.3758	0.08747
17	0.01	RMSprop	0.8709	0.5233	0.5123	0.4379	0.1608
18	0.001	RMSprop	0.8858	0.6722	0.4356	0.3952	0.0733
19	0.001	SGD	0.7963	0.4319	0.4386	0.3675	0.9431
20	0.01	SGD	0.8828	0.8528	0.1797	0.2246	0.4131
21	0.001	Adam	0.8971	0.6115	0.5210	0.4003	0.0599

Table 4. Learning Rate and Optimizer tweaking results on Learner-8.

Figure 12. Plot of learner metrics results from Table 3.

Figure 13. Plot of hyper-parameter tweaking results from Table 4.

S.No.	Drop Out	Batch Size	AUC	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Loss
1	0.1	30	0.8849	0.5443	0.5652	0.372	0.0459
2	0.2	100	0.8895	0.4659	0.6268	0.3744	0.1995
3	0.2	50	0.8789	0.4964	0.6129	0.3901	0.0309
4	0.4	30	0.8959	0.5941	0.5163	0.3794	0.1291
5	0.4	60	0.886	0.5003	0.6355	0.4112	0.327
6	0.4	100	0.8959	0.5875	0.5343	0.3616	0.1638
7	0.6	30	0.8926	0.6109	0.5282	0.3258	0.1916
8	0.6	50	0.894	0.4762	0.6025	0.3868	0.0714
9	0.8	30	0.9055	0.6326	0.47	0.346	0.1274
10	0.8	50	0.8933	0.6265	0.4753	0.3552	0.111

Table 5. Dropout Rate and Batch Size tweaking results on Learner-8.

Figure 14. Plot of hyper-parameter tweaking results from Table 5.

V.

CONCLUSIONS

We present a novel deep-learning approach for the detection of real-world anomalies in surveillance videos. Recognizing the intricacies of these genuine anomalies, relying solely on normal data might not be the most effective strategy for anomaly detection. Our method aims to leverage both normal and anomalous videos. To circumvent the labor-intensive process of temporally annotating anomalous segments in training videos, we opt for learning a general model of anomaly detection using a deep Multiple Instance Learning (MIL) framework with weakly labeled data. To validate our approach, we introduce a new extensive anomaly dataset encompassing diverse real-world anomalies. The experimental results on this dataset show that when compared to baseline techniques, our suggested anomaly detection approach performs noticeably better. The results indicate that our model outperforms other models in terms of AUC and has a significantly higher Recall and Precision.

Future work in this domain could include experimentation with a more comprehensive and diverse dataset, possibly combining UCF-Crime with ShanghaiTech and other such popular globally available datasets.

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